

Effect of treating seed with chemicals and antagonists on inhibiting seedborne pathogens and on germination, root length, shoot length, dry weight, and vigor indices.*

Treatment	Concentration (%)	Diameter of inhibition zone for <i>P. oryzae</i> (mm)	Diameter of inhibition zone for <i>H. oryzae</i> (mm)	Germination (%)	Root length (cm)	Shoot length (cm)	Dry weight (mg)	Vigor index based on root length and percent germination	Vigor index based on shoot length and percent germination	Vigor index based on dry matter and percent germination
Fungicide										
Pyroquilon	0.1	22.90 c	15.47 b	95.11 ab	16.12 fg	6.22 a	151.70 jk	1536.16 q	592.55 p	14441.78 q
Pyroquilon	0.2	30.11 ab	18.39 g	94.89 ab	16.50 efg	6.49 a	152.44 j	1565.90 p	616.67 o	14471.78 p
Pyroquilon	0.3	30.77 a	19.33 fg	93.78 b	16.37 fg	6.05 a	150.17 jkl	1536.22 q	568.25 q	14088.17 r
Tricyclazole	0.1	20.45 c-f	21.94 def	94.67 ab	16.99 d-g	6.61 a	158.22 i	1610.47 o	625.92 n	14989.56 o
Tricyclazole	0.2	27.44 b	25.06 cd	96.00 ab	18.81 a-f	7.18 a	164.61 gh	1808.12 j	689.65 i	15011.33 n
Tricyclazole	0.3	27.50 b	26.39 bc	95.56 ab	18.60 a-f	6.85 a	161.56 h	1782.84 l	655.10 l	15446.89 m
Carbendazim	0.1	15.22 ghi	22.22 def	95.34 ab	21.05 ab	7.77 a	175.56 ab	2054.78 b	755.73 b	17091.55 b
Carbendazim	0.2	21.56 cd	24.11 cde	97.11 ab	21.77 a	7.90 a	176.22 a	2119.58 a	769.75 a	17156.67 a
Carbendazim	0.3	22.11 cd	25.00 cd	97.33 a	20.53 abc	7.23 a	174.67 ab	1972.14 d	727.91 f	16771.33 e
Carboxin	0.1	14.83 hi	21.67 ef	96.00 ab	17.50 c-g	7.01 a	165.61 fg	1674.35 n	669.17 j	15830.67 k
Carboxin	0.2	18.22 efg	22.94 de	95.78 ab	20.31 abc	7.59 a	174.61 ab	1909.41 f	735.02 d	16884.22 c
Carboxin	0.3	19.06 def	24.00 cde	96.00 ab	19.77 a-e	7.59 a	172.94 bc	1892.87 h	694.81 h	16535.33 g
Mancozeb	0.2	14.11 i	29.50 b	94.67 ab	16.53 efg	6.82 a	165.61 fg	1562.86 p	646.74 m	15642.67 l
Mancozeb	0.3	19.67 def	33.28 a	95.56 ab	17.82 b-g	7.31 a	169.61 de	1703.46 m	699.04 g	16209.78 i
Mancozeb	0.4	19.72 def	33.00 a	95.34 ab	18.73 a-f	7.67 a	171.44 cd	1786.86 k	731.94 e	16347.11 h
Thiram	0.2	12.28 i	18.50 g	96.22 ab	19.76 a-e	6.84 a	173.72 abc	1901.47 g	658.44 k	16719.77 f
Thiram	0.3	15.06 hi	23.33 cde	97.11 ab	20.39 abc	7.67 a	175.03 ab	1980.98 c	745.37 c	17093.94 b
Thiram	0.4	17.50 fgh	24.84 cde	96.45 ab	20.03 a-d	7.61 a	174.61 ab	1941.22 e	735.00 de	16859.55 d
Antagonists										
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	60 × 10 ⁹ cfu/ml	15.06 hi	18.50 g	93.78 b	16.15 fg	5.99 a	149.33 kl	1515.89 r	562.49 r	13930.22 s
<i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i>	60 × 10 ⁹ cfu/ml	14.83 hi	19.83 fg	93.78 b	16.11 fg	6.04 a	147.78 lm	1512.69 s	553.41 s	13857.28 t
Carbendazim (0.2%) + <i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	60 × 10 ⁹ cfu/ml	21.22 cde	23.17 cde	94.67 ab	19.67 a-e	6.54 a	167.94 ef	1858.51 i	619.47 o	15939.78 j
Control		0.00 j	0.00 i	88.45 c	15.15 g	5.73 a	144.94 m	1341.63 t	507.18 t	12889.00 u
LSD (P = 0.05)		0.66	0.68	3.40	0.07	0.02	0.90	46.30	11.80	282.69

*Av of 3 replications of 6 mo of observations. Values followed by different letters in each column are significantly different (P = 0.05) by DMRT.

inhibition zone that developed around the seed was measured.

Seeds treated with pyroquilon (0.3%) had the largest inhibition zone for *P. oryzae*, followed by tricyclazole (0.3%), mancozeb (0.4%), and carboxin (0.3%). Seeds treated with mancozeb (0.4%) had the largest inhibition zone for *H. oryzae*, followed by tricyclazole (0.3%). Carbendazim and carboxin (both at 0.2 and 0.3%) also inhibited the pathogens (see table).

Treated seeds showed higher seedling vigor than untreated seeds. Seedlings raised from seeds treated with carbendazim (0.2%) and mancozeb (0.4%) had the best seedling vigor.

It is advisable to treat seeds with either pyroquilon or tricyclazole (0.2%) in areas

where BI and brown leaf spot disease are severe. These fungicides effectively inhibit the pathogens while maintaining vigorous seedlings. Significantly higher seedling vigor, germination percentage,

and inhibition of seedborne pathogens can also be obtained by treating seeds with carbendazim (0.2%) and mancozeb (0.3%). ■

Effect of foliar spraying of *Aspergillus terreus* Thom on sheath blight (ShB) and rice plant characteristics

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We tested the efficacy of *A. terreus* as an aqueous spore suspension spray in reducing incidence of ShB (*Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn).

The experiment was conducted during 1988 and 1992 ahu seasons (Apr-Aug). Twenty-six-day-old seedlings of rice cultivar IR50 were transplanted into 25-cm-diam clay pots containing 5 kg ricefield soil. *A. terreus* conidial suspension (47 × 10⁶ spores/ml in 1988 and 49 × 10⁶ spores/ml in 1992) was sprayed on foliage 38 d after transplanting in three ways: 3 d after, 3 d before, and simultaneously with inoculation of *R. Solani*. *R. solani*

ShB lesion size (mm²) after treatment with foliar spray of *A. terreus* spore suspension. Assam, India, 1988 and 1992 ahu seasons.

Days after spraying	1988					1992					
	<i>A. terreus</i> (no.)	<i>R. solani</i> alone	<i>R. solani</i> + <i>A. terreus</i> spray 3 d later	<i>R. solani</i> + <i>A. terreus</i> on same day	<i>R. solani</i> + <i>A. terreus</i> spray 3 d before	Mean ^a	<i>R. solani</i> alone	<i>R. solani</i> + <i>A. terreus</i> spray 3 d later	<i>R. solani</i> + <i>A. terreus</i> on same day	<i>R. solani</i> + <i>A. terreus</i> spray 3 d before	Mean
3		10.67	8.85	4.50	0.71	6.18 a	8.41	8.78	4.76	0.71	5.41 a
9		11.25	10.50	8.52	4.52	8.69 b	11.55	10.25	8.05	4.35	8.55 ab
15		11.68	11.70	12.24	8.70	11.08 a	12.42	11.87	9.96	6.41	10.17 bc
21		12.70	12.08	12.34	9.54	11.66 c	15.19	13.11	11.14	9.33	12.19 cd
27		14.05	15.68	14.15	11.01	13.72 d	16.01	14.91	12.59	11.53	13.76 de
33		16.80	16.04	14.64	11.45	14.73 d	18.14	16.36	13.40	12.68	15.14 def
39		17.85	16.51	14.79	12.41	15.39 d	20.16	16.94	14.24	13.40	16.18 ef
45		18.14	17.07	15.22	13.06	15.87 de	20.23	17.24	14.52	13.91	16.48 ef
75		20.70	18.15	15.78	13.16	16.97 e	21.53	17.80	14.79	14.00	17.03 f
Mean		15.86 a	14.06 b	12.46 c	9.36 d	15.96 a	15.96 a	14.03 b	11.49 c	9.59 d	
LSD (0.05):	Inoculation (I)		0.81				1.82				
	days (D)		1.40				3.16				
	I × D		ns ^b				ns				

^aMeans followed by different letters are significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bns = not significant.

Effect of foliar sprays of *A. terreus* spore suspension on growth characters of rice plants inoculated with *R. solani*.^a 1988, 1992.

^aMeans in a column with a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

inoculation without *A. terreus* served as control. Plants were inoculated with *R. solani* by inserting 12-d-old sclerotium (grown on potato dextrose agar) between individual sheath and culm. ShB incidence was recorded up to 75 d after spraying with *A. terreus* (see table).

Foliar spraying of *A. terreus* reduced ShB infection in all treatments in both years (see table). Maximum reduction, was obtained when *A. terreus* was sprayed before *R. solani*. Spraying after *R. solani* inoculation was the least

effective treatment. Significant differences existed among days of observation, with disease incidence progressively increasing with time.

Effect of sequence of inoculation and days after inoculation on disease incidence were significant. Differences among treatments were shown at many points along the disease progress curve.

Plant height and yield in 1988 and 1992, and dry weight of plant in 1992 were significantly greater in plants receiving *A. terreus* treatments than in the

control (see figure). Greater increases for all characters were obtained when *A. terreus* was sprayed either before or simultaneously with *R. solani* inoculation than when it was sprayed after *R. solani* inoculation. ■